

CONSTITUTIVE DESCRIPTIONS OF ACTIVE STRESS IN BLOOD VESSELS LEADING TO CONTRACTILE INSTABILITY

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SUMMARY

To model the contraction of blood vessels, an active stress component can be added to the (passive) Cauchy stress tensor. Different constitutive formulations have been used to describe this active stress component with varying parameterisations. In this work, we examine formulations for use with limited experimental contraction data as well as those developed to capture more comprehensive data sets. We show that a subset of these formulations exhibits unstable behaviour (i.e., a non-unique diameter solution for a given pressure) in certain parameter ranges, particularly when contractile deformations are large. Our work shows how limited contraction data complicates the selection of an appropriate active stress model for vascular applications.

Key words: *active stress, vascular contraction, smooth muscle cells*

1 INTRODUCTION

Blood vessel walls often contain vascular smooth muscle cells (SMCs) with contractile capacity, which allow for regulation of caliber to control tissue perfusion and to adapt to changes in blood pressure [1]. The relative arrangement and distribution of SMCs varies for different vascular segments, where elastic vessels such as the aorta contain elastic lamellae separating concentric layers of SMCs and more distal muscular arteries such as the femoral artery contain fewer lamellae and thicker layers of SMCs [2]. Furthermore, the vascular tone under similar loading conditions and vasoaggonist administration can vary across the circulation [3]. During disease processes, SMCs modulate their phenotype and adapt their active tone, which can both mitigate and contribute to pathological outcomes [4]. Therefore, quantifying changes in vascular contractility is critical to understanding disease development and identifying potential interventions.

Measured deformations during active contraction of blood vessels also depend on the passive material behaviour of the tissue. Biomechanical experiments carried out under a physiologic biaxial loading state on intact vessel segments have been used to simultaneously identify both passive and active behaviours [5]. The resulting data from these experiments have been captured with a variety of constitutive formulations aimed at understanding the changes in metrics relevant to clinical function and the underlying microstructural mechanisms.

In this work, we examine different active formulations used to capture the effects of vascular tone. All constitutive models herein are phenomenological and do not consider the specific kinetics of calcium handling and actomyosin activity that allow for contraction. As such, we focus on the robustness of each approach to generate appropriate deformation behaviour and limit mathematical difficulties for

the wide range of loading conditions and magnitudes of contractile deformation evident in different orders of the vasculature. This is particularly relevant as some active stress formulations have been found to encounter potential loss of ellipticity in the governing equations [6]. Models are investigated both analytically and with numerical simulations to understand potential difficulties in their use for capturing experimental data. We identify the potential for development of a limit point instability to occur under certain loading conditions for a subset of the constitutive models.

2 METHODOLOGY

As experiments are frequently performed on straight segments of vascular tissue, blood vessels are considered here as axisymmetric, cylindrical tubes. With this assumption, the only non-trivial linear momentum balance equation lies in the radial direction with $\frac{\partial t_{rr}}{\partial r} + \frac{t_{rr}-t_{\theta\theta}}{r} = 0$ where \mathbf{t} is the Cauchy stress tensor and r and θ are the radial and circumferential coordinates in the deformed configuration. This equation can be integrated to yield $P = \int_a^b \frac{t_{\theta\theta}-t_{rr}}{r} dr$ with P the transmural pressure and a and b the loaded inner and outer radii, respectively. Assuming an additive form for the active stress contribution, the Cauchy stress tensor can be written as $\mathbf{t} = -p\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{t}^{\text{pas}} + \mathbf{t}^{\text{act}}$. The passive part of the Cauchy stress \mathbf{t}^{pas} depends constitutively on the passive stored energy density Ψ^{pas} according to $\mathbf{t}^{\text{ex}} = \frac{2}{J} \mathbf{F} \frac{\partial \Psi^{\text{pas}}}{\partial \mathbf{C}} \mathbf{F}^T$ with deformation gradient tensor \mathbf{F} , right Cauchy-Green deformation tensor $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F}$, and $J = \det \mathbf{F} = 1$ under the assumption of incompressibility as commonly assumed for vascular tissue. A Lagrange multiplier p is used to enforce the incompressibility constraint, which can be found generally for any position within the wall using the traction boundary conditions.

For the active stress contribution in a blood vessel, a circumferential orientation for smooth muscle cells is generally assumed, yielding $\mathbf{t}^{\text{act}} = t^{\text{act}} \mathbf{e}_\theta \otimes \mathbf{e}_\theta$. For a convenient function Ψ^{act} to relate to the stored energy density for the active contribution, we can also write $t^{\text{act}} = 2F_{\theta\theta} \frac{\partial \Psi^{\text{act}}}{\partial C_{\theta\theta}} F_{\theta\theta}$, noting that Ψ^{act} is not a true energy density function but a mathematical construct. For pressurisation and axial extension of the blood vessel in the absence of torsion, $\mathbf{F} = \text{diag}[\lambda_r, \lambda_\theta, \lambda_z]$ with $\lambda_\theta = \frac{r}{R}$, λ_z prescribed based on experimental observations, and $\lambda_r = \frac{R}{r\lambda_z}$ due to incompressibility. We note that the equation balancing luminal pressure can be split into passive P^{pas} and active P^{act} components due to the additive combination of the stress contributions according to $P = P^{\text{pas}} + P^{\text{act}} = \int_a^b \frac{t_{\theta\theta}^{\text{pas}} - t_{rr}^{\text{pas}}}{r} dr + \int_a^b \frac{t^{\text{act}}}{r} dr$, noting that the radial component of \mathbf{t}^{act} is 0.

We examine five active stress formulations. The first three formulations each consist of a single material parameter representing a constant, deformation-independent stress. Their simplicity was motivated by the limited data often used for determining active stress to prevent overparameterisation. We define $t_c^{\text{act}} = T_c$ as a constant Cauchy active stress in the current configuration. Similarly, we define constant 1st Piola-Kirchhoff (PK) and 2nd PK active stresses as $t_i^{\text{act}} = \lambda_\theta T_i$ and $t_r^{\text{act}} = \lambda_\theta^2 T_r$, in the intermediate and reference configurations, respectively. More complex models motivated by contraction experiments under several loading conditions have been developed previously [7, 8]. The Rachev model captures the parabolic length-tension relationship according to $t_{Rv}^{\text{act}} = T_{Rv} \lambda_\theta \exp\left(-\frac{(\lambda_{\text{opt}} - \lambda_\theta)^2}{2\omega^2}\right)$, with T_{Rv} the maximum active stress generated at the optimal stretch λ_{opt} and ω controlling the response range [9]. Another relation, referred to here as the Zulliger model, is $t_{Zr}^{\text{act}} = T_{Zr} [\lambda_\theta \lambda_{\text{pre}} - \ln(\lambda_\theta \lambda_{\text{pre}}) - 1]$ and includes a stiffness-like parameter T_{Zr} and the pre-stretch of the SMCs λ_{pre} . For each of the five formulations, the potential for formation of a limit point instability is examined by taking the derivative of the pressure with respect to the loaded inner radius.

3 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

We first examine the case of a constant Cauchy active stress. In this case, $P_c^{\text{act}} = \int_a^b \frac{t_c^{\text{act}}}{r} dr = T_c \ln\left(\frac{b}{a}\right)$ and $\frac{\partial P_c^{\text{act}}}{\partial a} = T_c \frac{a^2 - b^2}{ab^2}$. As the loaded inner radius a is always smaller than the loaded outer radius b , $\frac{\partial P_c^{\text{act}}}{\partial a}$ is always negative, which can lead to unstable behaviour depending on the relative magnitudes of the passive and active stresses. A similar examination of a constant 1st PK stress can be written as $P_i^{\text{act}} = \int_a^b \frac{t_i^{\text{act}}}{r} dr = \frac{T_i}{\sqrt{\lambda_z}} \ln\left(\frac{B + \sqrt{B^2 - A^2 + \lambda_z a^2}}{A + \sqrt{\lambda_z} a}\right)$, where we have used the incompressibility constraint to relate the unloaded inner and outer radii (A and B , respectively) to their loaded counterparts according to $b = \sqrt{(B^2 - A^2)/\lambda_z + a^2}$. Taking the derivative of P_i^{act} with respect to the loaded inner

Figure 1: Experimentally measured contraction of the descending thoracic aorta of a male wild-type (C57BL/6J) mouse following addition of $1\mu\text{M}$ of phenylephrine to the vessel bath. Throughout the 15 min-long experiment, the artery was axially stretched to its *in vivo* length and pressurised at 90 mmHg. Data from [3].

radius a yields $\frac{\partial P_i^{\text{act}}}{\partial a} = T_i \frac{a(A+\sqrt{\lambda_z a})-b(B+\sqrt{\lambda_z b})}{b(A+\sqrt{\lambda_z a})(B+\sqrt{\lambda_z b})}$, which is also negative for all deformation states.

Finally, the constant 2nd PK active stress is examined, where $\int_a^b \frac{t_r^{\text{act}}}{r} dr = \frac{T_r}{2\lambda_z} \ln\left(\frac{B^2}{A^2}\right)$, which is constant for any pressure loading with $\frac{\partial P_r^{\text{act}}}{\partial a} = 0$ and therefore does not contribute to the potential for a limit point instability. Expressions for the Rachev and Zulliger models have more complex analytical solutions where the sign of the derivative of the pressure contribution is dependent on the parameter values chosen. These models were therefore only examined numerically here, along with the simpler active stress constitutive forms.

Alongside the theoretical derivation introduced above, we present a demonstrative case study in which these five formulations are used to model the mechanical behaviour of the contracted descending thoracic aorta (DTA) of an adult male C57BL/6J mouse. The objective of these simulations was to replicate the experimental result of the static contraction experiment in Figure 1. Briefly, using a biaxial testing setup, the mouse DTA was stretched to its *in vivo* length and pressurised to 90 mmHg. Then, $1\mu\text{M}$ of phenylephrine (eliciting SMC contraction) was added to the vessel bath and changes in outer diameter tracked for 15 minutes. For each active stress formulation, the active stress model parameters were adjusted to match the contraction attained in Figure 1; i.e., a 29% diameter reduction at 90 mmHg and *in vivo* axial stretch. The passive (i.e., fully relaxed) behaviour of the mouse DTA was modelled using a four-fibre family strain energy function (SEF): $\Psi^{\text{pas}} = \frac{c}{2}(I_1 - 3) + \sum_{i=1}^4 \frac{k_1^i}{4k_2^i} \left[e^{k_2^i(I_4^i - 1)^2} - 1 \right]$, where $c = 24.3\text{ kPa}$ is an elastin stiffness-like parameter, $I_1 = \text{tr}(\mathbf{C})$, $k_1^1 = 8.7\text{ kPa}$ and $k_2^1 = 0.19$, $k_1^2 = 13.6\text{ kPa}$ and $k_2^2 = 0.04$, and $k_1^3 = k_1^4 = 1.8\text{ kPa}$ and $k_2^3 = k_2^4 = 0.95$ are stiffness-like and non-linearity parameters for axial, circumferential, and diagonal collagen fiber families, respectively, and $I_4^i = \lambda_z^2 \cos^2(\alpha^i) + \lambda_\theta^2 \sin^2(\alpha^i)$ with $\alpha^1 = 0^\circ$, $\alpha^2 = 90^\circ$, and $\alpha^{3,4} = \pm 33^\circ$ for axial, circumferential, and diagonal fiber families, respectively. The SEF parameter values were taken from averages of the C57BL/6J control group in [3].

The modelled active behaviours are presented in Figure 2. Although, as demonstrated above, both the constant Cauchy and the constant 1st PK active stress models are prone to instability, for the modelled case, this phenomenon occurred only in the former (Figure 2A and B, respectively). The Ψ^{act} parameters were $T_c = 48.6\text{ kPa}$ and $T_i = 43.3\text{ kPa}$, respectively. Note that, due to the aforementioned instability, the constant Cauchy active stress model was not able to capture well the contraction measured experimentally, with the target contraction falling within the instability region (Figure 2A). In agreement with the analytical derivation, the constant 2nd PK SMC stress model ($T_r = 38.9\text{ kPa}$) led to an upward shift of the passive response, thus preserving the shape of the four-fibre family SEF (Figure 2C). Panels D and E in Figure 2 show modelled curves for the Zulliger [8] and Rachev [7] models, respectively. Note that, compared to the previous three formulations, these models are more complex, involving a minimum of 2 and 3 model parameters, respectively, for the fully contracted state (i.e., setting the vascular tone parameter to 1). It is, therefore, apparent, that such models are overparametrised to describe the experimental data in Figure 1 consisting of a single mapping point between the fully relaxed and the fully contracted state. Therefore, we choose to fix all model parameters except the SMC stiffness-like coefficients T_{Zr} and T_{Rv} to values reported in the original manuscripts; i.e., $\lambda_{\text{pre}} = 1.83$ (describing the SMC deposition stretch) for Zulliger's model [8] and $\lambda_{\text{opt}} = 1.4$ and $\omega = 0.45$ (describing the stretch of the peak SMC force and the width of the Gaussian stress-stretch relationship) for Rachev's model [7, 9]. This choice led to $T_{Zr} = 148.0\text{ kPa}$ and $T_{Rv} = 53.2\text{ kPa}$, respectively, to replicate the experimental data. While for these parameter choices

Figure 2: Simulated response to inflation at a constant (*in vivo*) value of axial stretch of the mouse descending thoracic aorta in both fully relaxed and maximally contracted conditions. Active behaviour was modelled using five different formulations.

neither of the two models led to instability, instability is theoretically possible with both models for certain areas of the parameter space (see examples in Figure 2D and E, lighter lines).

Overall, our results suggest that caution is warranted when using mechanical models to capture contractile behaviour in the absence of more extensive experimental data. Notably, the presence of limit point instabilities has also been observed experimentally for muscular arteries under certain loading conditions [10], stressing the need for careful application of modelling *and* experimental conditions to identify and simulate those states that are physiologically relevant.

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